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Improving VET student teachers' lesson planning competence: The analogy between lesson planning and scriptwriting for anchored instruction films

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Abstract

Learning how to plan a lesson is an important element of student teachers' professional development. There is a vast range of theories, models and guidelines to support this learning process. However, their theoretical bases, empirical evidence and practical benefits vary considerably. Moreover, lesson planning is frequently neglected by teacher education research. The evidence-based approach presented in this paper focuses on the improvement of the lesson planning competence of vocational education and training (VET) student teachers from a business and economics didactical perspective. The innovative idea of this concept is an analogy between lesson planning and scriptwriting for anchored instruction films. The accompanying research project hypothesises that students should plan more subject didactically based and sophisticated. Moreover, it can be assumed that they also focus the learning processes of individuals and their interactions.

Keywords

anchored instruction; lesson planning; teacher education research; teacher professionalisation

1 Introduction

Lesson planning is a basic competence of professional teachers. That is emphasised in national standards for teacher education, published by educational institutions like the German Standing Conference of the Ministers of Education and Cultural Affairs (KMK, 2014) or the British Department for Education (DfE, 2011). Hence, learning how to plan a lesson is an important element of student teachers' professional development.

A vast range of theories, models and guidelines exist that advance lesson planning. They emerge from different fields of research on teacher education and from practically oriented institutions. Therefore, the theoretical bases, the empirical evidence and the practical benefits of these elaborations vary considerably. Beyond that, lesson planning is frequently neglected by teacher education research, although teaching and assessing are often objectives of empirical studies (John, 2006; Rakhkochkine, 2011; Reigeluth, 1983).

In German teacher education, lesson planning is often a domain of general didactics (Arnold & Lindner-Müller, 2012). Because subject-specific objectives, contents, methods and media play an important role in lesson planning, it is greatly influenced by subject didactics as well.

As a result, there is a lack of advanced, subject didactically based teaching-learning arrangements to improve students' lesson planning competence and empirical studies on their effects.

The evidence-based approach introduced in this study focuses on the improvement of the lesson planning competence of VET student teachers from a business and economics didactical perspective. The innovative idea of the seminar is an analogy between lesson planning and

scriptwriting for anchored instruction films. This concept is the main issue of this paper. The accompanying research project hypothesises that students should plan more subject didactically based and sophisticated. Moreover, it can be assumed that they also focus on the learning processes of individuals and their interactions. First analyses of pre-post vignette tests show positive developments in the student teachers' lesson planning competence.¹

In chapter 2, a cursory overview of lesson planning theories, models and research is outlined. Based on this, the conceptual principles of the didactical design are described in chapter 3. The article concludes in chapter 4 using perspectives of the approach and the research project.

2 Lesson planning: cursory overview of theories, models and research

Apart from the above-mentioned guidelines for lesson planning, there is virtually a vast range of theories, models and research about this basic teachers' competence. The following remarks give a brief overview of these central works.

The task of lesson planning is quite extensive and complex. With a focus on student learning, teachers have to consider and integrate subject-specific objectives, contents, methods and media into their professional actions. Furthermore, educational aspects, such as planning lessons, are generally characterised by national discourses (Mutton, Hagger & Burn, 2011). Based on this variety of perspectives, the theoretical basis of lesson planning ranges from educational psychology, such as behaviorist, cognitivist or constructivist learning theories (Driscoll, 2005), to curriculum studies, such as curriculum theory, curriculum analysis or curriculum reform (Richards, 2018), and different didactical traditions, such as instructional design in North America (Reigeluth, 1983) or general didactics in Germany (Arnold & Lindner-Müller, 2012).

As lesson planning is significantly influenced by national frameworks, the subsequent outlines exemplarily refer to Germany.² Over the last several decades, different didactical models have been elaborated. They focus on specific issues in teaching and learning and their conditions. Hopmann (2000) points out that classical didactical models, such as Klafki's, often dominate university teaching-learning environments. However, it has been argued that lesson planning is not as linear as these models suggest (Mutton, Hagger & Burn, 2011).³ Moreover, these models often emerge from the general didactics field (Rakhkochkine, 2011), even though lesson planning is greatly influenced by subject didactics. In the German VET system, for instance, teachers have to consider vocational action competence as a specific educational objective. Beyond that, lessons are organised as so-called learning fields. Via this conception, curricula are based on work and business processes rather than subjects and refer to approaches of situated and problem-based learning (Mulder, Weigel & Collins, 2007). Sloane's (2009) didactical model integrates these aspects from a business and economics di-

¹ The approach is part of the business and economics didactical project "Improving professional (planning-related) action – anchored instruction" at the University of Kassel. It is funded within the framework of the joint "Quality Campaign for Teacher Education" by the German federal government and states and financed by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research, project number: 01JA1505.

² For an international perspective on theories, models and research on lesson planning, see Rakhkochkine (2011).

³ Regarding the classical didactical model of Tyler, John (2006) refers to a similar situation in the United Kingdom.

dactical perspective. These remarks imply that the theoretical framework of this concept is characterised by tensions between general and subject didactical insights into lesson planning.

Even though lesson planning – as a basis of teaching and assessing – is crucial, little research has focused on this teachers’ core task (Aprea, 2008; Mutton, Hagger & Burn, 2011). First, often-cited studies in the United States of America and Germany were published by Clark and Yinger (1979) and Bromme (1981). Currently, a considerable body of empirical work exists on this issue (Rakhkochkine, 2011). Early research focused on the technical conceptions of teachers’ lesson planning and was based on theoretical prescriptions for good plans and rational decision-making. Currently, psychological conceptions of lesson planning and the interplay between planning and teaching have been explored (Rakhkochkine, 2011).

This work is based on research projects on modeling and measuring the competence of lesson planning. They mainly refer to Shulman (1987) to conceptualise the knowledge components of teachers’ professional competence (Blömeke et al., 2008). Shulman (1987) distinguishes between content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and general pedagogical knowledge. *Content knowledge* “rests on two foundations: the accumulated literature and studies in the content areas, and the historical and philosophical scholarship on the nature of knowledge in those fields of study.” (Shulman, 1987, 9) *Pedagogical content knowledge* is defined as “that special amalgam of content and pedagogy that is uniquely the province of teachers, their own special form of professional understanding” (Shulman, 1987, 8), and *general pedagogical knowledge* refers “to those broad principles and strategies of classroom management and organisation that appear to transcend subject matter” (Shulman, 1987, 8). Overlaps and interrelations are reported between pedagogical content knowledge and general pedagogical knowledge. Therefore, defining the boundaries of these concepts is theoretically difficult (Blömeke et al., 2008; Messina et al., 2018).

By focusing on future teachers’ lesson planning competence, the three core domains of their knowledge have to be simultaneously addressed (Blömeke et al., 2008). In this regard, pedagogical content knowledge plays an important role, as it “represents the blending of content and pedagogy into an understanding of how particular topics, problems, or issues are organized, represented, and adapted to the diverse interests and abilities of learners, and presented for instruction.” (Shulman 1987, 8) Figure 1 illustrates these coherences.

Figure 1 Domains of knowledge of teachers’ professional competence and lesson planning

The identification of special aspects of lesson planning concerning pedagogical content knowledge⁴ on the one hand and general pedagogical knowledge⁵ on the other hand is therefore an interesting theoretical question that this research project explores.

Subsequently, the conceptual principles of the approach to improve the lesson planning competence of student teachers are outlined.

3 Conceptual principles of the didactical design

The teaching-learning arrangement at hand is intended for student teachers in the master's degree program for business and economics education at the University of Kassel. Against the objectives' background and seminar's contents, this chapter will focus on the students' core task: planning lessons with the assistance of the analogy between lesson planning and script-writing for anchored instruction films.

The main objective of the course is the advancement of the students' lesson planning competence (objective 1). By focusing on the relevant contents and the technical terminologies of the lessons to be planned, the students have to profoundly deal with economic sciences (objective 2). Moreover, they must take principles of business and economics didactics into account, such as action orientation, work and business process orientation, complex teaching-learning arrangements, situated learning and anchored instruction (objective 3).⁶ Not least, the students have to focus on pupils' individual requirements (objective 4) within iterative planning processes (objective 5).

At the beginning of the seminar, the student teachers reflect on their experiences with planning teaching-learning arrangements. Based on this, the discussion of established general and subject didactical models takes place. Their main objectives and benefits for lesson planning are focused on (see chapter 2). Subsequently, the introduction of Sloane's (2009) business and economics didactical model serves as a common and consistent theoretical basis for the prospective lesson plans. The model integrates the above-mentioned subject didactical principles and offers criteria with which to design teaching-learning arrangements within learning fields. Central questions concerning subject didactical (goal and educational orientation, situational adequacy and narrative embeddedness, process orientation, learning and working strategies) and technical (scientific adequacy and application of knowledge, reduction and transformation, generalisation) issues serve as guidelines for lesson planners.

The innovative analogy between lesson planning and scriptwriting for anchored instruction films is at the centre of the seminar. At the beginning of the planning process, teachers have to consider specific aims. They choose appropriate content and plan pupils' interactions. Scriptwriters also start their work with a story in mind. They imagine characters whose interactions lead the story line to fulfilling its purpose (Field, 2005). Scripts for anchored instruction films are focused, as anchored instruction – similar to business and economics didactics – refers to concepts such as situated and problem-based learning (Bransford et al., 1990).⁷

⁴ See Kuhn, Alonzo and Zlatkin-Troitschanskaia (2016) for fundamental research on pedagogical content knowledge in business and economics didactics.

⁵ See König et al. (2011) for fundamental research on general pedagogical knowledge in general didactics.

⁶ German business and economics didactics are significantly influenced by national discourses. Therefore, the definitions and the applications of the abovementioned principles are partly quite specific (Brockmann, Clarke & Winch, 2008; Gessler & Moreno Herrera, 2015).

⁷ The idea of analogy formation derives from approaches such as “design task” by Aprea (2008) and “lesson play” by Zazkis, Sinclair and Liljedahl (2013). Aprea (2008) uses the analogy in her

Subsequent to the exploration of the analogy, the basics of film production are introduced as templates for written lesson plans. Central instruments are the film sketch and the script. The film sketch is an outline of the lesson, briefly describing its aims, contents, methods and media. In the script, the actions of the teachers and pupils are edited in a scenic and dialogical shape. The film sketch and the script contain the teachers' goal-oriented activities and the pupils' anticipated activities.

After practicing these heuristics, the students plan lessons using the analogy of scriptwriting for anchored instruction films. They work together in pairs and conceptualise ninety-minute lessons. Regarding the contents, the students focus on the learning field "planning, managing and controlling procurement processes" of the "industrial business management assistant" occupation. The written lesson plans and specific reflection tasks are the basis of the students' performance assessment.

Figure 2 shows an example of an introduction of a lesson that was planned in the form of a script. Stage directions, monologues and dialogues characterise the lesson's chronological sequence. The planner's subject didactical reflections are highlighted with a grey background, and the technical reflections are located in the footnotes.

concept to coach business and economics education student teachers in planning lessons. The mathematics student teachers of Zazkis, Sinclair and Liljedahl (2013) plan lessons in the form of dialogues with a focus on subject-specific problems.

<p>Occupation: Industrial business management assistant Year of training: 2 Recommended time scale: 80 hours</p>	<p>Learning field 6: Planning, managing and controlling procurement processes</p>
<p>Thursday, 02 May 2018 07:50 a.m., teachers' room</p>	<p>← Stage direction</p>
<p>MARTIN MILLER (thinking):</p> <p>My lesson with the industrial business management assistants begins shortly. The 25 students (17 men and 8 women) will start with learning field 6 today. <i>According to the framework curriculum, the learners should be able to plan, manage and control the entire procurement process in the context of procurement logistics by the end of the learning field. In doing so, they must consider the procurement strategy to be part of the corporate strategy (KMK, 2002).</i></p> <p>We already elaborated an overview of industrial corporations' market-oriented business processes in learning field 2. This framework has been repeated by focusing on value-added processes in learning field 4 and the processes of production of goods or services in learning field 5.</p> <p>I would like to start with connecting to the available competences of advancing business processes. For this purpose, I ask the pupils to create an overview of industrial corporations' basic functions. Subsequently, they should assign the procurement processes to this overview. <i>The task is repetitive in nature. It will be easy to handle for all learners, so they should work individually.</i></p>	<p>← Subject didactical reflection regarding goal and educational orientation, situational adequacy and narrative embeddedness, process orientation and <i>learning and working strategies</i> in the form of a monologue (Sloane, 2009)</p>
<p>08:00 a.m., classroom MARTIN MILLER:</p>	<p>← Chronological sequence of the lesson</p>
<p>Good morning, dear students. Occasionally, the learners return the teacher's greeting.</p>	
<p>MARTIN MILLER:</p> <p>Today, we will begin with learning field 6. It covers the planning, managing and controlling of procurement processes. To keep track of the central business processes, please outline an appropriate model of an industrial corporation's basic functions¹ in your notebooks. Finally, highlight the procurement processes in your model. Work individually because the task is repetitive in nature. You have a total of 15 minutes.</p>	
<p>KATHRIN SCHMIDT:</p> <p>I have a question about our task. Do we have to name the management processes and core and support processes?</p>	<p>← Dialogue</p>
<p>MARTIN MILLER:</p> <p>Differentiating the processes already goes beyond the task. Please concentrate on an industrial corporation's basic functions. You should assign the procurement processes to these basic functions. Differentiating the processes will be subsequently addressed.</p> <p>The pupils start outlining appropriate models of an industrial corporation's basic functions.</p>	<p>← Technical reflection regarding scientific adequacy and application of knowledge, reduction and transformation and generalization (Sloane, 2009)</p>
<p>¹ <i>Industrial corporations' basic functions are task fields that are connected with contrary flows of goods and funds: 1. procurement, 2. production of goods or services, 3. sales and 4. funding (Hall et al., 2008).</i></p>	

Figure 2 Example of a lesson plan in the form of a script

The implementation of this teaching-learning arrangement should improve the students' lesson planning competence. The business and economics didactical basis is intended to advance the reference to the respective principles. By planning in scenes and dialogues, the students have to profoundly deal with the economic sciences, and they are encouraged to focus on individuals and their interactions. Finally, this kind of planning requires process orientation.

4 Conclusion

The teaching-learning arrangement was piloted in winter term 2015/2016 in a seminar with 27 student teachers. In winter term 2016/2017, the optimised concept was realised with 9 students. The advanced approach became part of the school-based teacher education course in winter term 2017/2018 with 18 students (Söll & Klusmeyer, 2018).

Prospectively, the innovative didactical design will be integrated with an e-portfolio conception, which improves students' lesson planning competence by making use of business and economics didactical prompts. The approach will also be adapted for all three phases of teacher education.

To examine the effects of the concept at hand⁸, pre-post vignette tests (Blömeke et al., 2008) supplement general evaluation tools, such as portfolios and questionnaires, in a parallel test research setting. The collected data are analysed using methods of qualitative content analysis (Saldaña 2016). The first exploration of the 84 paired vignette tests shows positive developments of the student teachers' lesson planning competence, operationalised through the quantity of the addressed categories. However, the explanations of coherences between the categories are partially absent or not very sophisticated. In-depth analysis will be applied in the near future.

In conclusion, the didactical design and the research project have the potential to improve the theory, research and practice of lesson planning and to support innovation in teacher education.

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⁸ The objectives of the concept are described in chapter 3.

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Biographical notes

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